

A study on Students' Preference towards E-books to Traditional Printed Books and its Impact on Sustainable Development.

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Traditionally, teachers and textbooks were considered to be the chief sources of knowledge for the students. However, with the penetration of internet and technology, it has opened up a new method of learning and acquiring knowledge and information which have changed the position of printed textbooks in learning space in the 21st century. Now, the students seek more knowledge and information source through e-book sources which are easily available at their convenient time and place on their device/gadget and necessarily from traditional knowledge source i.e., through printed books. It is not that today's students are different but the availability of technology, that they are exposed to have made this difference. This emergence of e-book, have created a paradigm shift in the acquisition of printed books, considering e-books as an alternative to printed books.

In this context an attempt has been made by the researchers to analyze the students' preferences towards e-books to printed books and its impact on sustainable development. For this purpose, data were collected from the student respondents of various colleges of Nagaon and Kamrup (Metro) districts with the help of structured questionnaire. The finding of the study has been discussed in details. Suggestions have also been made in the light of various findings for the benefits of the students and for the sustainability development. The findings and the suggestions will help the educational institutions and librarians in their decisions relating to investment and management of library resources very effectively. It will also help the writers/authors to tune/channelise their writings as per the demands of the students.

Keywords: Perception, Traditional printed books, e-books, sustainable development.